

Barriers and Enablers to Effective Maternal Health Campaigns on Social Media Platforms in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study was carried out to explore the factors that facilitate or hinder the effectiveness of maternal health campaign on social media platforms in Nigeria. The enablers include digital literacy by providing training to users on how to enhances their competence in using digital health tools, engaging community members in health campaigns had increased the confidence and satisfaction among service users, contributing to their trust in healthcare providers and healthcare systems and interactive feature of the social media platforms such as immediate feedback proves to be of advantage , while barriers examined in this study are digital divide such as poor network and misinformation on social media platforms proves to be a disadvantage to health outcomes. The researchers adopted the media richness theory, which argue that media choice influences message effectiveness. The researchers adopted the library research method. The findings revealed that despite the challenges of using social media for maternal health campaigns, these campaigns are seen to be effective by facilitating awareness on maternal health issues, promoting healthier maternal behaviour and extend reach of maternal information. This study suggested that government and private organisations should carryout orientations on digital literacy and limit digital divide in Nigeria. The paper concludes that social media platforms offer more good than harm in passing health information in Nigeria.

Keywords: Enablers, Barriers, Maternal Health, Social Media, Campaigns

Introduction

Maternal health remains a public health challenge in Nigeria, a country that accounts for a large part of global maternal mortality rate. According to World Health Organisation (2023), Nigerian maternal mortality rate is 1,047 deaths in every 10,000 live births. The lifetime challenges of a Nigerian woman dying during pregnancy, childbirth, postpartum or post abortion is 1 in 22; as against the lifetime risk in developed countries estimated at 1 in 4900 live births.” WHO (2023), reports that “in every 2 minutes, one Nigerian woman dies and for each casualty.” There are several women who will have lifelong problems and no access to medical care. Nigeria, is one of the countries with the highest maternal mortality rates in the world, where many women are facing barriers in accessing health care services during pregnancy and childbirth. Recently, social media platforms have become important tools for health communication, providing different ways to share